

Automated Parameterization of Quantum Mechanically Derived Force-Fields for Soft Materials and Complex Fluids: development and validation.

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Abstract

The reliability of molecular dynamics (MD) simulations in predicting macroscopic properties of complex fluids and soft materials, such as liquid crystals, colloidal suspensions or polymers, relies on the accuracy of the adopted force-field (FF). We present an automated protocol to derive specific and accurate FFs, fully based on *ab initio* quantum mechanical (QM) data. The integration of the JOYCE and PICKY procedures, recently proposed by our group to provide an accurate description of simple liquids, is here extended to larger molecules, capable of exhibiting more complex fluid phases. While the standard JOYCE protocol is employed to parameterize the intra-molecular FF term, a new automated procedure is here proposed to handle the computational cost of the QM calculations required for the parameterization of the inter-molecular FF term. The latter is thus obtained by integrating the old PICKY procedure with a fragmentation reconstruction method (FRM), that allows for a reliable, yet computationally feasible sampling of the inter-molecular energy surface at QM level. The whole FF parameterization protocol is tested on a benchmark liquid crystal, and the performances of the resulting quantum mechanically derived (QMD) FF compared with those delivered by a general-purpose, transferable one, and by a third, "hybrid" FF, where only the bonded terms were refined against QM data. Lengthy atomistic MD simulations are carried out with each FF on extended 5CB systems in both isotropic and nematic phases, eventually validating the proposed protocol by comparing the resulting macroscopic properties with other computational models and with experiment. The QMD-FF yields the best performances, reproducing both phases in the correct range of temperatures, and well describing their structure, dynamics and thermodynamic properties, thus providing a clear protocol that may be explored to predict such properties on other complex fluids or soft materials.

1 Introduction

Colloidal suspensions, liquid crystals (LCs) and polymers are all capable of spontaneously developing organized supramolecular structures.¹⁻⁴ The macroscopic properties of such complex fluids are often determined by a fascinating yet delicate balance between an entropic term, connected with the molecular shape and volume of their constituting elements, and an enthalpic term, essentially governed by supramolecular interactions.^{1,2,4-6} Therefore, only a deep insight, at molecular and atomic level, can help to clarify and rationalize the relationship between the molecular structure and the macroscopic properties of the resulting bulk phase, which is in turn pivotal to the design of novel soft materials of technological interest.^{5,7-9} Theoretical and computational approaches play an important role, because they provide direct access to the molecular structure. In this framework, classical molecular dynamics (MD) simulations^{10,11} are among the most popular computational tools to tackle structure-properties investigations, as they allow for achieving the required microscopic insight and, at the same time, for an adequate sampling of the phase-space visited by the system.¹² Nowadays, MD simulations flank and integrate experimental findings on supramolecular features, exploiting a level of detail unattainable in real experiments.¹³⁻¹⁷

Nonetheless, the reliability of MD predictions heavily relies on the accuracy of the force field (FF) adopted to describe the investigated system.^{10-12,18} This requirement is particularly severe when dealing with soft materials and complex fluids.^{18,19} In fact, all terms concurring to condensed phase stability, including non covalent interactions, molecular flexibility, confined conditions, etc., should be dealt with similar (high) accuracy, if the balanced interplay among the different players has to be well reproduced. Several recent studies focused on typical supramolecular systems as polymers,²⁰ self assembled soft materials,^{14,15} solvated proteins,²¹ or LCs,^{16,19,22} have pointed out the necessity of a partial FF refinement or even of a complete re-parameterization, thus embracing the idea of less transferable yet more accurate FFs, specifically tailored for the investigated systems. To this end, the significant increase in computer power of the past two decades has permitted to resort to accurate quantum mechanical (QM) methods, able to yield reliable reference data, over which specific FFs can be parameterized.

Exploiting this possibility, several automated or semi-automated methods have been proposed that are able to deliver such quantum mechanically derived force fields (QMD-FFs).^{19,23–60} Although all these procedures are rooted in the possibility of deriving FF parameters based on selected QM data, they present different features, according to which they may be classified. One possible criterion is to consider the type of FF parameters employed: most of the aforementioned QMD-FF procedures concern either with the description of the single molecule flexibility (intramolecular or valence FFs),^{23,27,28,31,34,37,40,49,50,52,60} with the interaction between two or more species (intermolecular or non-covalent FFs)^{24,25,32,39,41,43,45,48,55,56,61} or with both these aspects simultaneously.^{30,33,35,38,42,53,54,57–59,62} Alternatively, the different QMD-FFs can be also classified based on the complexity of their defining model functions. Indeed, exploiting the wealth of information contained in the parent QM description, more complex and physically motivated models can be adopted in the FF definition, allowing, for instance, to separately account for three body terms, polarization effects, dispersion interactions, etc.^{35,39,42,48,50,56,57,59} However, the significant loss in computational speed has often limited their application in simulations of large and complex systems. In these cases, considering both the computational benefit and the straightforward availability in the most popular MD simulations engines, QMD-FFs can be more conveniently parameterized employing the standard simple potential functions, namely 12-6 Lennard-Jones (LJ), point charges, harmonic potentials and Fourier series.^{23,27,30,38,43,45,49,51,53,54,58,61,62}

Among complex soft materials, LCs^{2,6} are one of the most challenging benchmarks for FF accuracy.^{19,63} On the one hand, collective motions, as re-orientational dynamics or the formation of smectic layers, involve large bulk regions and take place on hundreds of nanoseconds,^{2,64} thus requiring a noticeable computational effort to reliably sample the spanned phase space. On the other hand, the structure and thermodynamic stability of the mesogenic phases is driven by a subtle interplay among the shape and flexibility of the phase-constituting molecules and the balance between a plethora of non-covalent forces, ranging from simple dipole-dipole to more complex π - π or hydrophobic interactions.^{2,65} Such quintessential properties are seldom accounted for by general-purpose FFs, and at least a partial refinement is usually required. In the past two decades, several groups have followed this route,^{16,22,25,26,29,66–77} achieving sig-

nificant improvements with respect to standard transferable FFs. Such refinement concerned either the intra- or the inter-molecular term, and was carried out based on QM data, experimental reference properties or both. For instance, Zannoni, Muccioli and co-workers have shown that the straightforward adoption of a general-purpose force-field leads to an overestimation of about 120 K on the nematic-to-isotropic transition temperature (T_{NI}) while a significant improvement can be achieved by a re-parameterization of the dihedral terms on QM calculations, followed by a intermolecular LJ re-parameterization, based on the experimental density.^{63,67,72} Similarly, Wilson's group reported⁷⁷ errors on transition temperatures, obtained with the standard GAFF parameters, which range from 30 K up to 200 K, and proposed an optimization of the intermolecular LJ parameters for LC's building blocks, which leads to a dramatic improvement on many thermodynamic properties, including the order parameter and the prediction of a new dark conglomerate phase.^{22,77} Even more recently, Poll and Sims have observed de Vries behavior in an extended simulation of a smectic liquid crystal,¹⁶ confirming that^{19,63} the FF re-parameterization of the bonded model potentials ruling flexible dihedral rotation, the atomic point charges, and/or the inter-molecular LJ parameters is the most effective route to accurate LC simulations.^{19,63}

Also in our group a long-lasting effort has been devoted to refine FFs suitable for LCs simulations.^{25,26,29,66,70,71,73,74,78,79} The basic idea underlying our approach consists in exploiting the classical partition of the total FF energy in an intra-molecular term and a inter-molecular one, and parameterize them separately, solely based on accurate QM data, yet employing only standard and computational effective model potential functions. According to this protocol, the former term is handled through the JOYCE approach,^{27,34,50} which delivers all the parameters of the bonded potentials (i.e. bond stretching, angle bending and dihedral torsions) and the intra-molecular non-bonded ones (the so called 1-4 LJ interactions^{10,11}) through a global fitting of QM reference data. The inter-molecular term is also fully-reparameterized (in terms of both point charges and LJ parameters) against a purposely computed QM database. In the early implementations of this approach,^{25,26,29,70,71,74,78,79} such database consisted in a collection of interaction energies computed over a number of dimer arrangements, built *a priori* by shifting and rotating as a rigid body one monomer with respect to the other. This protocol was applied

to few benchmark liquid crystals (namely 5CB,^{25,26} *p*-quinquephenyl,⁷¹ 8CB,⁷⁴ 5OCB,²⁹ and HAB⁷³) and its transferability tested on their homologue series.^{29,70,78,79} The results strongly supported the adoption of QMD-FFs in LC simulations: the intrinsic predictive capability of the QMD-FF approach, which in principle is capable of delivering valuable performances even when the availability of training experimental data is scarce or absent, as in the design of novel species, was enforced by the global improvement achieved in the reproduction of the LC structure^{25,26,71,74} and dynamics.^{29,73,78–80}

The main drawback of the aforementioned approach consisted in an overestimation of the bulk density,^{26,29,71,73} which in turn caused a significant error in the prediction of translational diffusion properties,^{73,78–80} thus limiting the reliability of MD's predictions. It was then hypothesized⁷³ that the collection of dimer configurations could be biased by both the rigid monomer geometry approximation and the user-defined nature of the selected dimer arrangements. To address these issues, a new inter-molecular QMD-FF parameterization procedure, PICKY, has been developed,^{33,38} and thoroughly tested on several simple liquids.^{51,58,81} The PICKY protocol derives the whole set of intermolecular FF parameters by minimizing the QM/FF interaction energy differences computed over a large set of dimer geometries. Yet, rather than being user-defined, the dimer arrangements are instead iteratively extracted from MD trajectories carried out along the parameterization procedure, hence solving in principle both the rigid monomer geometry issue and the reliability of the dimer geometries employed to sample the interaction potential energy surface (IPES). Despite the encouraging results achieved for different kinds of simple liquids,^{33,38,51,58,81} these preliminary applications evidenced the importance of both *i*) an accurate and computationally efficient QM method and *ii*) an exhaustive sampling of distinct dimer configurations. Although this endeavor is manageable for simple liquids, in LC composed by significantly larger molecules the sheer size of the problem (mostly stemming from the increased monomer dimensions and subsequent enlargement of dimer configuration space) renders the approach computationally daunting and ultimately compromises PICKY's wide applicability/use.

The automated approach presented in this work aims to fill this lack, making thus possible to extend QMD-FF parameterization to large molecules, capable to yield stable supramolec-

ular architectures as liquid crystalline mesophases. It integrates the most recent advances of the aforementioned JOYCE⁵⁰ and PICKY⁵¹ protocols with the Fragmentation Reconstruction Method (FRM),⁶⁶ a procedure devised to significantly decrease the computational cost in the QM calculation of the interaction energy of non-covalent complexes composed by large and flexible molecules.^{66,82} Regarding the former, it is important to emphasize that it deals with non-covalent inter-molecular interactions between dimers, at variance with more commonly employed covalent (intra-molecular) fragmentation schemes.^{22,35,53,54,57,62,77} To test the reliability of the whole QMD-FF parameterization protocol, a complete intra- and inter-molecular parameterization is carried out for a nematogenic molecule, the 4-cyano-4'-*n*-pentylbiphenyl (5CB), which is probably the most popular benchmark liquid crystal employed in computational studies.^{19,26,63,66,68,72,76,83,84} Furthermore, concomitant to the critical assessment of the QMD-FF performances in LC properties predictions, the present study provides the opportunity to gain a deeper insight onto the separate role of the reliable representation of the molecular flexibility (accounted by the intra-molecular term) and the accurate description of the molecular interactions (entailed in the intermolecular term) in determining the final results. To this end, lengthy MD simulations are carried out on one thousand 5CB molecules employing three different FFs of increasing specificity: namely the general-purpose OPLS^{85,86} FF, an alternate "hybrid" FF, assembled by coupling the former intermolecular transferable parameters to the QM derived intra-molecular term (obtained with the JOYCE procedure), and the QMD-FF derived with the here proposed protocol. The outcomes of the investigated FFs are then employed to characterize both 5CB's isotropic and nematic phase, comparing the computational results among them and with experiment, in terms of structure, dynamics and thermodynamic properties.

2 Methods

The total FF potential energy of any complex fluid (E_{tot}^{FF}) can be expressed as a sum of an intra-molecular FF term, E_{intra}^{FF} , ruling the flexibility of each molecule and an inter-molecular term,

E_{inter}^{FF} , accounting for the interaction among the molecules composing the system:

$$E_{tot}^{FF} = E_{intra}^{FF} + E_{inter}^{FF} \quad (1)$$

In case of homogeneous condensed phases, the intra-molecular term is clearly the same for each molecule, hence, for a system of N_{mol} molecules

$$E_{intra}^{FF} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{mol}} u_i^{intra} \quad (2)$$

where u^{intra} takes the standard expression,

$$u^{intra} = u_s + u_b + u_{st} + u_{ft} + u_{nb}^{intra} \quad (3)$$

and u_s , u_b , u_{st} , u_{ft} and u_{nb}^{intra} are the potential terms related to stretching, bending, stiff and flexible torsions and non-bonded intra-molecular interaction, respectively (see eq. (S2) to (S5) in the Supporting Information). On the same foot, E_{inter}^{FF} is computed through a pairwise sum,

$$E_{inter}^{FF} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{at}} \sum_{j=i}^{N_{at}} u_{ij}^{inter} \quad (4)$$

where N_{at} is the number of atoms of each monomer, i and j are dummy indexes running over the atoms of two different interacting molecules, and u_{ij}^{inter} takes the standard LJ + Coulomb term expression:

$$u_{ij}^{inter} = 4\varepsilon_{ij}^{inter} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}^{inter}}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}^{inter}}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right] + \frac{q_i q_j}{r_{ij}} \quad (5)$$

where ε_{ij}^{inter} and σ_{ij}^{inter} are the LJ 12-6 parameters and q_i and q_j the point charges.

The general protocol adopted to build and validate a QMD-FF according to equation (1) is sketched in the flow chart displayed in Figure 1. As shown in the top left corner, the only information required to start the procedure is the chemical formula of the target nematogen, here the 5CB molecule. The first step of the whole procedure consists in computing, at the chosen QM level of theory, few selected data for one 5CB monomer. With such reference, the intra-molecular term E_{intra}^{FF} can be obtained employing the well tested JOYCE procedure,^{27,34,50,58} as briefly described in the following paragraph. Next, exploiting the classical energy partition

Figure 1: Flow chart of the QMD-FF parameterization procedure applied to 5CB.

expressed in equation (1), the resulting intra-molecular QMD-FF term, E_{intra}^{FF} , can be coupled to a trial inter-molecular term $E_{inter}^{FF_0}$, defined for instance with a starting set of transferable parameters. The resulting "hybrid" FF, $E_{tot}^{FF_0}$, is employed in preliminary MD runs, whose trajectories can be used as starting point of the new PICKY-FRM parameterization protocol (vide infra). The new procedure is aimed to overcome the computational burden associated with the QM calculation of the interaction energy of the 5CB's dimers, required by the PICKY procedure, by implementing within the PICKY code an automated version of the FRM protocol⁶⁶ (bottom left inset in Figure 1), allowing for the calculation of hundreds of dimers at feasible computational cost. Finally, as shown in the bottom right of Figure 1, once the PICKY-FRM parameterization is converged, the QMD-FF intermolecular-term, E_{inter}^{FF} , is coupled with the JOYCE intra-molecular term E_{intra}^{FF} , and the resulting E_{tot}^{FF} eventually employed in lengthy MD simulation at constant pressure and selected temperatures, to investigate 5CB's condensed phases.

The intra-molecular term, E_{intra}^{FF} , defined in equation (2) and ruling each monomer flexibility, is parameterized once and for all according to the JOYCE protocol,^{27,34,50} using the QM database computed specifically for the 5CB molecule, consisting in the optimized geometry, its Hessian matrix and the relaxed torsional energy scans along selected flexible dihedrals. The

parameterization is carried out by minimizing, through a linear fitting, the standard JOYCE objective function:

$$I^{intra} = \frac{1}{N_{geom}} \sum_g^{N_{geom}} W_g \left[\Delta E_{intra}^{QM} - u^{intra} \right]_g^2 + \sum_{K \leq L}^{3N-6} \frac{2W''_{KL}}{(3N-6)(3N-5)} \left[H_{KL}^{QM} - \left(\frac{\partial^2 u^{intra}}{\partial Q_K \partial Q_L} \right) \right]_{g=0}^2 \quad (6)$$

where W_g and W''_{KL} terms are user-defined weights, the first sum runs over the N_{geoms} conformations of the 5CB monomer considered in the QM relaxed scans, and ΔE_{intra}^{QM} is the QM internal energy. The second sum runs over the QM normal modes, where H_{KL}^{QM} is the QM Hessian matrix evaluated at the equilibrium geometry ($g = 0$), while Q_K is the K^{th} normal coordinate and N the number of atoms. Further details about the parameterization are included in Section 1 of the Supporting Information or can be found in the original papers.^{27,34,50}

The inter-molecular term, E_{inter}^{FF} , defined in equation (4) is parameterized according to the new PICKY-FRM automated procedure, as outlined in the following:

- α) All 5CB point charges are obtained at QM level, through the CM5 method⁸⁷ applied to the optimized geometry. To take into account polarization effects, the charge localization procedure is performed accounting for the environment through the continuum PCM model,⁸⁸ considering benzonitrile as solvent.
- β) At difference with previous PICKY parameterizations carried out on simple liquids, where a global optimization of all inter-molecular parameters is performed,^{33,38,51,58,81} here a different strategy is followed, aimed to ease the transferability toward potentially interesting larger homologues. Concretely, since the OPLS FF is known to deliver reliable and accurate results for aliphatic chains,⁸⁵ the LJ inter-molecular parameters of the aliphatic carbons and their hydrogens are transferred from OPLS, and thereafter constrained during the successive parameterization. On the one hand, considering the good performances of this general purpose FF on hydrocarbons, such a choice should impact negligibly on the final QMD-FF's accuracy. On the other hand, the resulting QMD-FF can be straightforwardly employed, without further re-parameterization, in the simulation of mesogenic compounds which share the same cyano-biphenyl core but differ in the aliphatic chain elongation, e.g. n CB mixtures or m CB n species.

- γ) The remaining LJ parameters (namely those describing the cyano group, all aromatic atoms and the first methylene unit attached to the second phenyl ring) are obtained through the new integrated protocol, which combines the PICKY^{33,38,51} and FRM⁶⁶ procedures, as described in the next points.
- δ) Similarly to the standard PICKY procedure, an initial MD run is carried out by combining the JOYCE intra-molecular QMD-FF with a starting set of intermolecular parameters, here transferred from the OPLS database⁸⁵ (see also Table F in the Supporting Information). The final equilibrated configuration is then used to extract a number of 5CB interacting dimers, in different arrangements chosen according the PICKY algorithm.³³

Figure 2: Scheme of the FRM applied on each dimer pair selected by PICKY.

- ε) The interaction energy of each sampled non-covalent dimer is now computed through the FRM scheme,⁶⁶ shown in Figure 2: each 5CB monomer is automatically fragmented by the new PICKY code⁸⁹ into three moieties, and the interaction energy of the whole dimer is reconstructed as the sum of the interaction energies of all possible fragment

pairs. Figure 3 illustrates how the FRM is integrated within the PICKY flux. First, dur-

Figure 3: Scheme of the FRM implementation within the PICKY suite of tools. Blue boxes: PICKY steps at cycle c (see previous section; green boxes: input and output data and pertinent PICKY tool; gray boxes: external codes (QM calculations and MD engine); red boxes: FRM activated tasks

ing the dimer sampling step, the original PICKY code has been modified to fragment each selected dimer according to the input specifics (essentially the atom numbers to be assigned at each fragment and the intruder type) and to automatically create a number of input files for each fragment or intruder pair, ready for the QM calculation. Next, once the QM calculations have been carried out, the second development concerns with building and updating the QM database at each cycle through the *pickyrecover* tool. In the present implementation, this tool is now able to automatically re-group all the fragment and intruder GAUSSIAN09 output files, reconstruct the interaction energy for each dimer, and store all data (i.e. energies and the corresponding whole dimer geometries) in a QM database of the proper format, with which the subsequent PICKY steps can be continued as usual. Further details can be found in the PICKY manual, freely available at <http://www.pi.iccom.cnr.it/picky>.

η) The QMD-FF intermolecular parameters are obtained by minimizing, through a non linear fitting, the standard PICKY objective function,^{33,38,51}

$$I^{inter} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_i^{N_{dim}} W_i \left[\Delta U_{inter}^{QM} - E_{inter}^{FF} \right]_i^2 ; C = \sum_i^{N_{dim}} W_i \quad (7)$$

where N_{dim} is the number of sampled dimer geometries, W_i a Boltzmann-like weight and ΔU_{inter}^{QM} the intermolecular energy for dimer computed at a proper QM level (see computational details).

ζ) The parameters found in step η) are employed, again combined with the QMD-FF intramolecular part, in MD simulations, and the parameterization procedure iterated from step ϵ) until convergence is achieved.

Further details about the parameterization of the intermolecular term can be found in the original PICKY papers^{33,38,51} or in the Supporting Information (Section 2).

3 Computational Details

The general-purpose OPLS FF for the 5CB molecule was built using the LigParGen tool,⁸⁶ hence obtaining a complete list of all the required bonded and inter-molecular parameters (see also Table F in the Supporting Information). Turning to the QMD-FFs, as mentioned in the previous section, the total FF potential energy E_{tot}^{FF} given in equation (1) is obtained by the separate parameterization of the intra- and inter-molecular terms. As previously shown for the benzene molecule,³⁸ the effect of the chosen intramolecular term on the PICKY parameterization is negligible, thus allowing to separately select the most convenient QM method to build intra- and inter-molecular reference data required for the QMD-FF parameterization. In any case, all QM calculations were carried out with the GAUSSIAN09 code.⁹⁰

The QM data required for the parameterization of E_{intra}^{FF} are specifically obtained for the 5CB monomer resorting to Density Functional Theory (DFT). In view of both its computational convenience and the well-known reliability in handling ground-state geometries, we resorted to the standard B3LYP-DFT functional, coupled with the Dunning’s correlation consistent cc-pvDz basis set. The optimized geometry is obtained by minimizing the 5CB’s internal energy

with respect to all degrees of freedom, while the Hessian matrix is computed at the global minimum after a careful check of all resulting vibrational frequencies. Finally, the relaxed torsional energy scans were carried out by optimizing all internal coordinates but the scanned dihedral.

As far as the E_{inter}^{FF} parameterization is concerned, the QM calculations consist in computing the interaction energy, ΔU_{inter}^{QM} , for hundreds of selected 5CB dimers. To limit the computational cost of such extended QM sampling, while not losing the required accuracy, we resorted to the highly efficient MP2^{mod} approach.^{29,91-95} According to the MP2^{mod} protocol, the interaction energy of a given non-covalent complex can be computed with the standard Möller-Plesset second order perturbation theory (MP2), but using modified basis sets of small dimensions, specifically optimized^{91,93,95} to reproduce few reference data.^{96,97} In this work, all inter-molecular energies were computed at MP2^{mod} level, making use of the modified cc-pvDz(0.37,0.41) basis set, where the exponents of the polarization d and p functions of the heavy and hydrogen atoms were set at 0.37 and 0.41, respectively. In fact, as recently reported in previous PICKY applications on simple liquids constituted by aromatic molecules,^{38,51,93} MP2^{mod} was found to outperform popular DFT functionals combined with several empirical dispersion corrections both in computational convenience and in accuracy with respect to reference interaction energies. Moreover, the cc-pvDz(0.37,0.41) MP2^{mod} modified basis set has been already optimized and validated by some of us²⁹ for a very similar nematogen molecule, hence no further basis set optimization nor computationally demanding reference calculation is required before performing the MP2^{mod} calculations.

All MD simulations in the NPT or NVE ensembles were carried out with the GROMACS code,⁹⁸ on systems of 1000 molecules. During PICKY cycles, 1 ns NPT runs were carried out keeping temperature and pressure constant through the Berendsen algorithm,⁹⁹ while all bond lengths were constrained to their equilibrium value through the LINCS algorithm,¹⁰⁰ and the time step set to 1 fs. Longer NPT equilibration (200 ns) and production (40 ns) runs were carried out at different temperatures using the final QMD-FF, the "hybrid" FF and the pure OPLS one. Both the LINCS algorithm and the 1 fs time-step are again adopted in these runs, but temperature and pressure were kept constant through the velocity-rescale¹⁰¹ and Parrinello-Rahman¹⁰² schemes,

which are capable to preserve the correct statistics in the NPT ensemble. Unless stated otherwise, in all NPT runs a distance cut-off of 12 Å was employed for short-range interactions, and the standard correction for energy and virial^{10,11} applied to LJ potentials. Conversely, long range electrostatic was accounted for by the particle mesh Ewald scheme (PME). Temperature and pressure coupling constant τ_T and τ_P were set to 0.1 ps and 5 ps, respectively. Finally, to access to dynamic properties, 20 ns MD runs were also carried out in the NVE ensemble, reducing the time step to 0.1 fs and removing all constraints on stretching terms.

MD equilibration was assessed by monitoring the bulk density and the second and fourth order parameters, P_2 and P_4 . The density, ρ , was computed as

$$\rho = \frac{M}{\langle V \rangle} \quad (8)$$

where M is the total mass and $\langle V \rangle$ the average volume. The second order parameter P_2 corresponds to the largest eigenvalue of the Saupe ordering matrix,^{2,19,63} defined as

$$Q_{ab} = \left\langle \frac{1}{2}(3u_a u_b - \delta_{ab}) \right\rangle \quad (9)$$

where, the mean value $\langle \dots \rangle$ indicates an average over all molecules composing the system, \mathbf{u} ($a = x, y, z$) is the 5CB's molecular long axis, and δ_{ab} is the Kronecker *delta*. Finally, the fourth rank order parameter P_4 can be computed as

$$P_4 = \left\langle \frac{1}{8}(35\cos^4(\theta) - 30\cos^2(\theta) + 3) \right\rangle \quad (10)$$

where θ is the angle between the principal molecular axis \mathbf{u} and the phase director \mathbf{n} , defined as the eigenvector of the Saupe matrix corresponding to P_2 .

The microscopic structure of the resulting isotropic and nematic phases was investigated by inspecting the pair correlation functions $g(r)$, $g(r_{\parallel})$, $g(r_{\perp})$ and $G_2(r)$, where $g(r)$ is the standard isotropic correlation function, whereas r_{\parallel} and r_{\perp} are the projections of the center of mass vectors along and normal to the phase director \mathbf{n} , respectively. The orientational correlation function $G_2(r)$ is obtained averaging, over all pairs of molecules and simulation time, the second Legendre polynomial of the angle between the principal axes of two molecules i and j as a function of their distance,

$$G_2(r) = \langle P_2(\hat{u}_i \cdot \hat{u}_j) \rangle(r) \quad (11)$$

It is worth mentioning that $G_2(r)$ reaches the asymptotic value of $(P_2)^2$ at large r .¹⁰³

Finally, the isotropic translational diffusion coefficients D , as well those projected along (D_{\parallel}) and perpendicularly to (D_{\perp}) \mathbf{n} were computed as the long time limit of the center of mass mean square displacement (MSD), *i.e.*

$$D_x = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{6t} \langle [\mathbf{R}_x(t) - \mathbf{R}_x(0)]^2 \rangle; \quad x = 0, \parallel, \perp \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_x(t)$ is the position of the molecular center of mass at time t , and $\langle \dots \rangle$ means a double average over all configurations and molecules. For the nematic phase, the longitudinal (D_{\parallel}) and transverse (D_{\perp}) diffusion coefficients were computed, by means of equation (12), from the positions \mathbf{R}_{\parallel} and \mathbf{R}_{\perp} projected onto and perpendicular to the phase director \mathbf{n} . More details can be found in Section 4 of the Supporting Information.

4 Results

4.1 OPLS simulations

A set of preliminary MD simulations were carried out with the general-purpose OPLS FF,^{85,86} in the NPT ensemble on systems of 1000 5CB molecules, at ambient pressure and increasing the temperature in the [400 K - 500 K] range in steps of 20 K. By controlling the P_2 order parameter along each run, the nematic to isotropic transition temperature could be tentatively placed between 440 K and 480 K, suggesting an overestimation (~ 150 K) of the experimental value, similar to the ones reported in literature for similar transferable parameters.^{22,63,77} Based on these results, two production runs were carried out, at 460 K and 480 K, monitoring the bulk density ρ and the order parameters P_2 and P_4 along both runs. All three properties are displayed in Figure 5, confirming the presence of an orientationally ordered phase, at a temperature, 460 K, well above the experimental nematic range, and the consequent necessity of a FF refinement. To separately investigate the role of intra- and inter-molecular parameterization, an "hybrid" approach was first attempted, consisting in joining the OPLS intermolecular description with a QM derived intramolecular part, specifically parameterized according to the JOYCE protocol²⁷ as described in the following. It is important to stress that a successful reproduction of the isotropic and nematic properties with such "hybrid" FF would mean that

only a specific and accurate representation of the intra-molecular flexibility is required to ensure reliable predictions, without the need of further computational burden, concerning with the inter-molecular part.

4.2 Intra-molecular parameterization

The QM optimized geometry of the 5CB monomer is shown in Figure 4.a. The molecule is composed by 38 atoms, and can be viewed as three building blocks, namely benzonitrile, phenyl and *n*-pentane (see also Figure S1). In agreement with previous studies,^{24,66} the two aromatic

Figure 4: Summary of the results of JOYCE parameterization. a) Overlap of the QM (orange solid) and QMD-FF (shaded blue) optimized geometries; b) correlation plot (left panel) between QM and QMD-FF computed vibrational frequencies and overlap (right panel) between QM and QMD-FF normal modes; c) QM (red circles) and QMD-FF (blue lines) relaxed torsional energy scan of the flexible dihedrals ϕ , δ_1 – δ_4 , whose definitions are given in the inset.

rings are not co-planar, and the aliphatic chain’s skeleton lies on a plane perpendicular to the one containing the central ring. The first two moieties are rather rigid, i.e. characterized by “stiff” internal coordinates. On the contrary, the aliphatic chain is flexible, and, as evidenced by the torsional energy relaxed profiles displayed in Figure 4.c, rotations are allowed around each C-C bond within the pentyl unit (δ_2 – δ_4). Moreover, a certain degree of flexibility was found also between two consecutive units, with rather low barriers separating different local minima

resulting in the torsional profiles (ϕ and δ_1 shown in Figure 4.c).

JOYCE parameterization was carried out for the 5CB molecule as described in the Methods section, obtaining a final standard deviation of less than 0.1 kJ/mol. All the final intra-molecular QMD-FF parameters defining E_{intra}^{FF} are reported in the Supporting Information in Tables A-E. The results of preliminary tests, devised for a first evaluation of the JOYCE E_{intra}^{FF} term quality, are briefly summarized in Figure 4, where the almost perfect overlap between the QM and FF optimized monomer structures (in Figure 4.a), is confirmed by the root mean squared deviation (RMSD), computed for the two geometries in terms of internal coordinates: 0.00 Å, 0.03° and 2.0 ° on bond lengths, bending angles and dihedrals respectively. On the same foot, the very good agreement between QM and QMD-FF frequencies shown in Figure 4.b evidences the adherence of the classical description to the parent QM PES in the region around minimum. Finally, considering the quantitative match of the ΔE_{intra}^{QM} and E_{intra}^{FF} torsional profiles shown in Figure 4.c, a reliable FF representation of the whole QM configurational space is to be expected also for larger distortions.

4.3 "Hybrid" FF simulations

The "hybrid" FF was assembled straightforwardly through equation (1), i.e. by combining the JOYCE parameterized intra-molecular term, E_{intra}^{FF} , with the inter-molecular part, $E_{inter}^{FF_0}$, taken from the OPLS database^{85,86} (see Table F in the Supporting Information for a full list), and employed in a preliminary NPT simulation, where the system of 1000 5CB molecules was first cooled at 400 K, still observing an isotropic liquid phase. The final configuration was then employed as starting point of two NPT separate runs, carried out for 200 ns at 380 K and 360 K again monitoring, as shown in Figure 5, the bulk density ρ and the order parameters P_2 and P_4 . It appears that in both 360 K and 380 K runs, the bulk density reached its equilibrium value in few ns, i.e. 978 kg/m³ and 956 kg/m³. This is in agreement with previous experiments¹⁰⁴ (960 kg/m³ at ~370 K). The results of the "hybrid" FF also show the formation of an orientationally ordered fluid at the lower temperature, where both the order parameters are found to increase toward asymptotic values typical of a nematic phase,^{2,19,63} i.e. ~ 0.6 and 0.25 for P_2 and P_4 , respectively. However, the real 5CB fluid at 360 K is clearly in its isotropic phase, being the

Figure 5: Bulk density (ρ , top) and order parameters (P_2 , center, and P_4 , bottom) monitored along the MD runs performed at 460 K (cyan) and 480 K (orange) with the "pure" OPLS FF and at 360 K (blue) and 380 K (red) with the "hybrid" JOYCE/OPLS FF.

experimental nematic-to-isotropic transition temperature (T_{NI}^{exp}) between 305 and 310 K.^{104–108} On the contrary, based on the two MD runs performed, the transition from a nematic to an isotropic phase for this "hybrid" FF would be tentatively located around 370 ± 10 K, still with a severe overestimation of about 60 K far from the experimental value, but significantly closer than the one predicted by the "pure" OPLS. The reason of the overestimated tendency of the 5CB molecules to stack and align, registered with the OPLS FF, should be therefore searched in some inaccuracy of the bonded term, and appears clearly by looking at Figure 6 where the dihedral population during the MD runs with the two FFs are compared. In fact, although the chain dihedrals δ_2 and δ_3 distributions registered for the two models show very similar features, more significant differences arise when the inter-ring dihedral ϕ and the ring-chain dihedral δ_1 are considered, rooted in an inaccurate description of the relative torsional potentials, as shown in Figure S2 of the Supporting Information. The main consequence, as shown in the upper pan-

Figure 6: 5CB's dihedral distributions (see Figure 4 for labeling) achieved with the MD runs carried out with the general purpose FF and the "hybrid" JOYCE/OPLS at the investigated temperatures: 460 K (cyan) and 480 K (orange) with the former FF and at 360 K (blue) and 380 K (red) with the latter.

els of Figure 6, is that the general-purpose description predicts a too much planar structure for the 5CB biphenyl core, which in turns favors the intermolecular stacking and, hence, the dimer alignment. Conversely, the "hybrid" FF corrects this issue and predicts less planar and more realistic monomers. However, it still appears to overestimate the 5CB self assembling forces, thus leading to an oriented phase stable at temperatures significantly above the experimental transition. It is therefore apparent that a general purpose and transferable intermolecular FF fails in giving quantitative results for 5CB, even when coupled to a refined bonded term, reinforcing our idea that in these cases refined inter-molecular FFs are also required to increase the accuracy of the MD predictions.

4.4 Inter-molecular parameterization

Before starting the intermolecular parameterization, a first set of fifty different 5CB dimers was extracted from the equilibrated configuration of the isotropic phase obtained at 380 K with the "hybrid" JOYCE/OPLS FF, and thereafter employed to evaluate the accuracy of the FRM implementation. This is achieved by computing the interaction energy of each dimer at MP2^{mod}/cc-pvDz(0.37, 0.41) level, with and without applying the fragmentation/reconstruction algorithm. Table 1 collects the main information retrieved from this test (see also Figure S3): in line with

RMSE	1.6
MAE	6.9
AUE	1.9
CPU benefit	13

Table 1: Statistical analysis in terms of root mean squared error (RMSE, kJ/mol), maximum absolute error (MAE, kJ/mol) and average unsigned error (AUE, kJ/mol) of the FRM reconstructed dimer interaction energies computed at MP2^{mod} level over the first fifty 5CB pairs selected in the first PICKY cycle with respect to the ones computed directly on the whole dimers, over the same arrangements. In the last line, the gain in CPU time (hours/processor) is also reported.

previous applications of the FRM protocol to this and other non-covalent dimers,^{25,29,66,73} the loss of accuracy is ~ 1.6 kJ/mol in average, yet with a significant benefit in terms of CPU time, thus allowing to confidently perform calculations on the large number of dimers geometries required by PICKY sampling.

Once the reliability of the FRM energies has been assessed, the parameterization of intermolecular parameters entering equation (5) was carried out following the specific protocol detailed in Table G of the Supporting Information, according to the PICKY-FRM stepwise procedure outlined in the Methods section. The atomic point charges, specifically computed for the 5CB mesogen at QM level according to step α , and the LJ parameters describing the aliphatic chains, transferred in step β from the OPLS database,⁸⁵ are reported in detail in Table 2 and F in the Supporting Information and were kept unaltered during all successive PICKY cycles. The motivation underlying this choice, stems from the fact that point charges remain almost unaltered for deformations experienced by each molecule within the liquid (further details in Figure S5). Conversely, all the remaining LJ inter-molecular parameters, i.e. those describing

At. type	q	At. type	q	At. type	q	At. type	q
N	-0.422	C ₃	0.014	C ₈	-0.146	H ₅	0.106
C _N	0.211	C ₄	-0.022	C ₉	-0.154	H ₆	0.105
C _B	-0.004	C ₅	-0.095	C _T	-0.236	H ₈	0.090
C ₁	-0.066	C ₆	-0.103	H ₁	0.122	H ₉	0.080
C ₂	-0.093	C ₇	-0.006	H ₂	0.112	H _T	0.079

Table 2: 5CB point charges q (e^-), computed at MP2^{mod}/cc-pvDz(0.37,0.41) level with the CM5 scheme.⁸⁷ Atom types refer to those shown in Figure S1 in the Supporting Information.

the aromatic cyano-biphenyl core and the methylene group attached to the central ring, were determined through the PICKY-FRM procedure.

The PICKY-FRM iterations were carried out with the settings detailed in Table G. It is here worth noticing that the temperature of the MD simulation performed at the end of each PICKY cycle was gradually decreased by 10-20 K until 340 K in the last cycle. Concomitantly, we carefully monitored the P_2 order parameter to check the absence of any orientational order (see also Figure S4). As a matter of fact, in agreement with the findings of previous parameterizations,³⁸ it is of the foremost importance that the PICKY sampling algorithm extracts a collection of dimers capable to reliably represent a significant region of the reference IPES. In this regard, performing the sampling in ordered fluids could favor the extraction of aligned dimers with respect to more random arrangements, hence biasing the resulting QMD-FF. Figure 7 shows the effectiveness of the PICKY sampling algorithm. The top left panel shows the distribution of the 550 inter-molecular energies, computed at QM level through the FRM, over the PICKY selected dimers. From this panel it is apparent that the sampling covers a wide range of values (from -60 kJ/mol to +10 kJ/mol) in a well distributed manner, being the exception the peak registered in the proximity of 0 kJ/mol. This peak was expected, as both dimers in very close contact and well far away from each other contribute to increase its intensity. A further confirmation of the sampling reliability is displayed in Figure 7.c, where the balanced distribution of selected geometrical descriptors (see panel b) for definition) clearly appears along the extracted dimers.

The PICKY-FRM parameterization converged successfully in six cycles, reaching the threshold $\Delta P < 1$ kJ/mol, see equation (S6), when 550 5CB dimers were eventually sampled. Table

Figure 7: Analysis and validation the PICKY sampling: a) distribution of the computed FRM QM inter-molecular energies over the collection of extracted dimers; b) definition of inter-molecular geometrical descriptors Ψ and Ξ in terms of long axis \hat{u} and inter-molecular distance \hat{R} ; c) distribution of inter-molecular center of mass distance (R) and Ψ and Ξ angles over the extracted dimers.

3 reports the behavior of selected quantities along the PICKY-FRM cycles, while further details are provided in Section 3 of the Supporting Information. The RMSE σ_P , between the

Cycle	sampled dimers	σ_P	ΔP
0	50.	2.97 (3.95)	-
1	50	1.08 (3.35)	2.62
2	150	1.46 (2.67)	2.41
3	250	1.57 (2.31)	3.65
4	350	1.88 (2.06)	2.81
5	450	2.05 (2.00)	1.14
6	550	1.95	0.98

Table 3: PICKY parameterization cycles in terms of some relevant quantities. σ_P (kJ/mol) is the weighted RMSE obtained as the square root of the objective function (7). Its value with respect to all 550 dimer is also reported in parenthesis. ΔP (kJ/mol) is the convergence index defined by equation (S6) and computed over more than $5 \cdot 10^5$ grid points in the dimer configurational space.

QM sampled IPES and E_{inter}^{FF} , always remained below the thermal energy (~ 3 kJ/mol), increasing as usual^{38,51,58,81} as the QM database dimensions are augmented, but only slightly in the last two cycles, suggesting that further sampling should not alter sensibly the shape of the QM

IPES. To control this hypothesis, the RMSE was recomputed over all the 550 sampled dimers with the parameters of each cycle, and the computed values are also reported in Table 3, where the increased accuracy with respect to the QM database at each cycle appears more evidently. The final σ_P is smaller than 2 kJ/mol, and the best-fit QMD-FF inter-molecular parameters are reported on Table 4.

Atom type	σ	ϵ	Atom type	σ	ϵ
N	3.090	0.7376	C ₆	3.244	0.7179
C _N	4.406	0.0050	C ₇	3.499	0.0091
C _B	3.116	1.4241	C ₈	3.417	0.3492
C ₁	3.752	0.0865	H ₁	2.351	0.1130
C ₂	3.498	0.5361	H ₂	2.121	0.0762
C ₃	3.280	1.3110	H ₅	2.486	0.0972
C ₄	4.489	0.0097	H ₆	2.495	0.0121
C ₅	3.507	0.4506	H ₈	2.761	0.0050

Table 4: Final QMD-FF LJ inter-molecular parameters, σ (Å) and ϵ (kJ/mol), specifically derived for 5CB from a QM IPES computed at MP2^{mod}/cc-pvDz(0.37,0.41) level. Atom types refer to those shown in Figure S1 in the Supporting Information.

4.5 QMD-FF simulations and final validation

The PICKY-FRM parameterized inter-molecular term, E_{inter}^{FF} , was eventually coupled with the JOYCE E_{intra}^{FF} part to yield the final QMD-FF, and successively employed in a series of MD runs. The temperature was gradually lowered by 20 K, from 340 K, where no ordered phase was observed during parameterization, to 300 K, i.e. below the experimental transition temperature. Similarly to Figure 5, where the results obtained for the hybrid JOYCE/OPLS are shown, Figure 8 displays the same properties monitored along the new QMD-FF runs at 320 K and 300 K. The top panel shows that within few ns the bulk density converges to its equilibrium value, which in turn is in good agreement with prior experiments (dashed lines) for both phases. Concretely, the predicted densities at 300 K and 320 K are $1015 \pm 3 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $990 \pm 3 \text{ kg/m}^3$, in very close agreement with experiment ($\sim 1019 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and 995 kg/m^3 , respectively).^{104,106} Therefore, in contrast with previous QMD-FFs,^{24,26,78} PICKY-FRM significantly improves the accuracy of the bulk density.

Figure 8: Bulk density (ρ , top) and order parameters (P_2 , center, and P_4 , bottom) monitored along the MD runs performed at 300 K (blue) and 320 K (red) with the JOYCE/PICKY-FRM QMD-FF. Dashed lines indicate experimental density¹⁰⁶ and order parameters.¹⁰⁹

To monitor the orientational properties, P_2 and P_4 order parameters are displayed in the two bottom panels of Figure 8. Also in this case, the spontaneous fluid re-organization into a orientationally ordered phase is apparent at lower temperature, whilst at higher ones the system remains isotropic. At variance with the "hybrid" FF, here the re-ordering is a slower process, as it requires over 150 ns to stabilize P_2 at a value larger than 0.4. Once equilibrated, the ordered phase exhibits a P_2 of 0.60 ± 0.03 and P_4 of 0.26 ± 0.03 , again in good agreement with the experiment (0.57 and 0.10).^{109,110} Yet, the most striking difference with the "hybrid" JOYCE/OPLS FF is the predicted transition temperature. If with the former it could be placed around 370 ± 10 K, thus overestimating the experimental T_{NI}^{exp} by 60 K, the specific E_{inter}^{FF} provides a significantly more accurate estimate. Based on Figure 8, the transition could be in fact tentatively placed between 300 K and 320 K, thus no more than 10 K far from T_{NI}^{exp} .^{104–108} Although a precise assessment of T_{NI} would require further simulations (e.g. large number of runs, different temperature ranges, cooling/heating sequences),^{19,63,71} by the reasons aforementioned one ought to expect a significant accuracy gain via the PICKY-FRM procedure.

The differences in the microscopic structure of the two phases, as represented at 320 K and 300 K, were investigated in more detail through the analysis of both positional and orientational correlation functions. The top panel of Figure 9 shows the comparison between the standard

Figure 9: Positional and orientational pair correlation functions computed over the NPT production runs carried out at 320 K (red lines) and 300 K (blue lines) with the JOYCE/PICKY-FRM QMD-FF. Top: standard center-of-mass pair correlation functions $g(r)$; center: pair correlation functions projected along the phase director \mathbf{n} ; bottom: orientational pair correlation functions $G_2(r)$ and P_2^2 (dashed line).

center-of-mass pair correlation function, $g(r)$, computed at 300 K and 320 K, i.e. in the nematic or isotropic phase, respectively. As expected for a LC phase, only negligible differences can be found in $g(r)$: the nematic phase shows a slightly more intense peak, showing a more structured first neighbor shell, but the positional order is lost in both cases before 15 Å. Yet, considering the intrinsic isotropic character of the $g(r)$ functions, the presence of positional order in one specific direction, as found e.g. in smectic phases,^{2,19,63} cannot be excluded only based on the radial distribution functions. The presence of smectic layers can be however excluded by looking at the pair correlation functions projected along the phase director, $g_{||}(r)$, which reveal the absence of positional order even along \mathbf{n} for both temperatures. Hence, the resulting ordered phase at 300 K can be safely classified as nematic. A further proof is given by the bottom panel of Figure 9, which compares the orientational correlation function $G_2(r)$, computed through

equation (11) over the two MD trajectories: at 320 K, in the isotropic liquid, $G_2(r)$ converges toward zero, whereas at 300 K, in the nematic phase, its asymptotic value (~ 0.36) correctly coincides¹⁰³ with P_2^2 .

The final validation test for the QMD-FF concerns with translational dynamics. One of the

Figure 10: Translational diffusion in the isotropic liquid (red lines) and in the LC nematic phase (bluish lines). Top: mean squared displacements averaged along the three Cartesian coordinates (isotropic), along the molecular long axis (parallel) or perpendicular to it. Bottom: diffusion coefficients as a function of simulation time.

major lacks of the previous parameterization strategy^{26,70} was the significant underestimation of the translational diffusion coefficients, which for the nCB series resulted⁸⁰ almost five times smaller than their experimental counterparts.^{80,111–113} It is therefore interesting to verify if the new parameterization strategy is capable to achieve a better description of 5CB's dynamics. The top panel of Figure 10 shows the MSD computed according to equation (12) in the isotropic liquid at 320 K and in the nematic phase at 300 K. While in the former only the isotropic diffusion (i.e. averaged over the three Cartesian coordinates) is considered, in the nematic phase also the displacement along and transverse to the molecular long axis is taken into account. It is evident that in all cases the linear regime is reached only after more than 1 ns, i.e. after a considerably longer time with respect to simple liquids. This is reflected in the behavior of

the diffusion coefficients along the simulation time, displayed in the bottom panel of Figure 10, where all curves reach their long time limit very slowly, and full convergence is not reached even after 8 ns, as evidenced in the inner panel. Besides the expected higher value of the isotropic coefficient in the disordered liquid at 320 K with respect to the averaged D value in the nematic phase, it can readily be observed as the diffusion along the long axis is significantly faster than that in a perpendicular direction, again confirming the nematic nature of the ordered phase.^{2, 19, 63}

To summarize all the validation tests, the final diffusion coefficients are reported together with other computed properties in Table 5, and compared to the experimental measures. The

Property	Nematic (300 K)		Isotropic (320 K)	
	QMD-FF	exp. [ref]	QMD-FF	exp. [ref]
ρ (kg/m ³)	1015 \pm 3	1019 [106]	990 \pm 3	995 [106]
P_2	0.60 \pm 0.03	0.57 [109]	0.09 \pm 0.03	0.0 [109]
P_4	0.26 \pm 0.01	0.10 [109]	0.01 \pm 0.01	0.0 [109]
D_{iso} (10 ⁻¹⁰ m ² /s)	0.40 \pm 0.02	0.37 [111]	0.85 \pm 0.03	0.80 [111]
D_{\parallel} (10 ⁻¹⁰ m ² /s)	0.70 \pm 0.02	0.66 [111]	-	-
D_{\perp} (10 ⁻¹⁰ m ² /s)	0.26 \pm 0.02	0.27 [111]	-	-

Table 5: Summary of some relevant computed properties of the 5CB liquid and LC phases, either measured^{106, 109, 111} or computed in this work with the QMD-FF.

almost quantitative agreement found for all computed D coefficients enforces the quality of the QMD-FF, capable to well represent also 5CB dynamics as well as its structural and orientational properties. Indeed, it is noticeable that a parameterization strategy based essentially on a faithful representation of the QM IPES succeeds in predicting also the dynamic properties with an almost quantitative accuracy.

5 Conclusions

The procedure herein discussed extends our previous QMD-FFs parameterization strategies,^{27, 33, 34, 38, 50} successfully carried out on simple liquids,^{24, 51, 58, 81} to simulations of complex fluids, as for instance LCs, where automated strategies for FF refinements are known to be requisite for reliable predictions.^{16, 22, 25, 26, 29, 67–72, 74–77} The present implementation of the Fragmentation Reconstruction Method⁶⁶ onto the PICKY protocol^{33, 58} has in fact allowed for the development of an

original and automated QMD-FF parameterization procedure, suitable for the rather large and flexible mesogenic molecules.

As a first application, we have investigated the PICKY-FRM performances in the prediction of the condensed phase properties of a benchmark liquid crystal, the 5CB nematogen. The results achieved with the QMD-FF demonstrate the unprecedented accuracy gain thus brought in. First, the FRM implementation into PICKY has been proven successful: the computational benefit gained with FRM now allows for accurate QM calculations of the interaction energy of several hundreds of dimers. Next, the dimer selection algorithm has been proven capable of a reliable sampling of the IPES visited by the large and flexible non-covalent dimers, as those usually characterizing complex fluids. Finally, the bulk density predicted by the present QMD-FF agrees almost quantitatively with the experimental values reported in literature for the two phases, thus indicating that the PICKY-FRM iterative procedure corrects the bias in the sampled dimer database that affected previous attempts to build a QMD-FF for 5CB,^{25,26} and eventually led to a significant density overestimation.

More importantly, the QMD-FF predicts both nematic and liquid phase in the correct range of temperatures, showing, upon cooling, a spontaneous reordering from the isotropic liquid, and the insurgence of a stable nematic phase. This was confirmed at microscopic level by the structural analysis carried out over the MD trajectories of the two 5CB's condensed phases and by the quantitative agreement with experiment found in both isotropic and anisotropic translational diffusion coefficients, which strongly suggests that also the 5CB's dynamics is well reproduced by the QMD-FF. All together, the computed properties seem to indicate a predicted nematic-to-isotropic transition temperature in excellent agreement with the experimental range, although further calculations would be needed to locate the transition more precisely. On the same foot, the slow spontaneous alignment of the molecular long axes through collective fluctuations, observed along almost 100 ns of simulation, would call for further investigations, to gain a deeper insight in the variation of intramolecular and intermolecular features, which might take place during the transition process.

Beside testing the applicability of the new procedure to LC phases, the present work also allowed us to critically assess the separate role of different FF descriptors on the overall accu-

racy of the computed properties. It has been shown that both the intra- and the inter-molecular parameters of general purpose FFs should be carefully re-parameterized to obtain a satisfactory level of accuracy. On the one hand, tailoring a specific description of the monomer flexibility, significantly increases the accuracy of the MD predictions with respect to the reference OPLS simulations. On the other hand, an accurate intramolecular parameterization alone does not allow for predicting the behavior of a complex fluid with a sufficient precision. In fact, only resorting to a refinement of the intermolecular term, the ordered and disordered phases can be simulated in the correct temperature range, whereas the use of transferable LJ parameters for the aromatic core lead to a anisotropic phase more than 60 °C above the real transition temperature. Nonetheless, it is worth noticing that the possibility to safely transfer at least the LJ parameters for aliphatic chains from a general-purpose database has two important consequences. First, it could pave the way to the straightforward extension of the present QMD-FF to larger nCB or similar homologues, without the need of any additional calculation. Furthermore, it also eases the parameterization of other classes of potentially mesogenic compounds, often characterized by the same flexible hydrocarbon lateral chains, but connected to different aromatic rigid cores.^{2,6} In this framework, the PICKY-FRM parameterization procedure could be applied to a number of LC forming molecules of increasing dimensions, to better determine the degree of transferability of the QMD-FF description.

A final, more general consideration concerns with the possibility of extending PICKY-FRM parameterization to other complex fluids or binary systems. The present implementation allows in principle to parameterize QMD-FF for any target flexible molecule forming complex fluids, but further applications will be necessary to evaluate if the same accuracy here obtained for 5CB is achievable for other different species. Yet, considering the computational burden connected with the lengthy MD runs and the extended systems required to investigate collective properties such as spontaneous self-assembly, the application of the PICKY-FRM protocol to other species appears to be beyond the present aims, but it will be the subject of future investigations. As far as the extension to binary systems is concerned, the procedure now works under the limiting condition of homogeneous systems, i.e. constituted by only one molecular species. It would be interesting to verify if the same degree of accuracy could be achieved in the prediction for

instance of the properties of LC mixtures, or, more in general, complex fluids with multiple components as co-polymer melts or colloidal suspensions. Notwithstanding some recent progresses have been reported in this direction,⁵⁵ up to our knowledge a complete and automated protocol to yield QMD-FFs for binary or multi-components systems has not been yet proposed, but the present findings encourage further attempts.

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Supporting Information

Additional details on the general intra- and inter-molecular parameterization protocols, discussion and data concerning the PICKY-FRM parameterization of 5CB, additional simulation results.

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